

CONSTRAINTS FACED BY THE MEMBERS OF DAIRY CO-OPERATIVE SOCIETIES

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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted during year 2018 in Kagal, Karveer and Hatkanagle tahsils of Kolhapur district of Maharashtra state to find Constrains faced by members of Dairy Co-operatives societies. Response from 150 milk producing farmers were collected from 15 villages and Ex post facto design of social research used for the present investigation.

It was found that the most serious constraints encountered by the members in different areas of breeding, feeding, management, health care and fodder production. The study concluded that co-operative dairy members faced a problems viz, high cost of improved cattle breeds, increase in expenditure on cattle management, fodder and labour in dairy enterprise. Impracticability in using highly technosive machineries due to small herd size, lack of land availability for fodder cultivation and pasture management, difficulty in controlling contagious and parasitic diseases of animals were the constraints in dairy enterprise. They also faced the constraint that lack of training programmes to raise the knowledge regarding dairy enterprise.

The study concluded that co-operative dairy members made suggestions like; knowledge should be given regarding handling of machine milking and enhance in milk price for the producers, the loan amount for the purchase dairy animals should be increased, loan sanction procedure should be easy, there should be training programmes regarding recent dairy technology practices at regular interval and subsidies should be given on certain inputs like veterinary medicines, fodder, seeds, concentrate, ration, etc. There should be regular and planned supply of vaccine and better co-ordination between office bearers, planning and executive staff with co-operative dairy members.

(Key words : Dairy co-operatives societies, socio-economic impact, milk)

INTRODUCTION

Milk is produced and consumed throughout the world and, in almost all the countries. India has the largest cattle and buffalo population in the world. Cows and buffaloes are the main milch animals, contributing 96% of the total milk production of the country. The willful efforts of people and government, reflected through successful implementation of programmes like "Operation Flood", transformed India from its deficit state in milk production to the world's largest milk producing country (Kunte and Patankar, 2015).

The Indian dairy farming is basically a small holder production system, almost 70 per cent of milk producers in India are landless, small and marginal farmers characterized by milk production by the masses rather than mass milk production. More than 80 million households (about 73 per cent of rural households) keep some type of livestock. Small

and marginal farmers who maintain one or two milch animals of low genetic potential for milk production primarily fed on crop residues and by-products and reared with the help of unemployed family members mostly female members. It has been emphasized that dairy development provides subsidiary occupation to a large section of the society particularly to the people living in the draught prone, hilly, tribal and other remote areas where crop production on its own may not be capable of engaging them fully.

The dairy co-operative society is found to be an important organization in the rural area because; it brings the rural producer and urban consumer to the direct control through elimination middlemen. It gives scope for functional specialization and division of responsibility between primary societies and the federations. The farmers concentrate on production and later take care of marketing. It gives incentives to producers by providing assured market; remunerative price and yearly bonus out of profits. Government programmes are easily routed through

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dairy co-operative societies. Producers can become educated in the latest knowledge on dairy farming through co-operatives. Co-operatives ensure involvement of milk producers in the management and decision making and provide collective bargaining power to the producer. The milk co-operatives have tremendous impact on socio-economic aspect of the members. The members get enough secondary income, employment to the family members and better marketing facility of the milk.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The qualitative and quantitative data were collected during year 2018 from Kolhapur district which comprised of 12 tahsils and out of these 3 tahsils namely Hatkanangale, Kagal and Karveer were selected purposively on the basis of maximum milk collection. The list of villages of each selected tahsils was obtained from Extension personnel from the co-operative dairy sangh on the basis of maximum milk collection. Five villages from each tahsil were selected by random sampling method and selection of co-operative dairy societies was done as one co-operative dairy society from each village. 15 co-operative dairy societies were selected. Ten dairy farmers who are the member of concerned co-operative dairy societies were selected from the 15 villages. Thus, the total sample size of the study was 150 members.

Questionnaire was prepared for primary data like age, education, size of family, annual income, herd size, dairy farming experience, land holding, cropping pattern, risk orientation, extension contact, and social socio-economic impact. The data processing was carried out after the collection from the field and was analyzed by using Ex post facto design of social research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Problems faced by the respondents

The information pertaining to the problems faced by the member respondents in the dairy business activities is given in the Table 1. Careful examination of results presented in Table 1 revealed that majority (90.66 per cent) of the respondents reported a problem that cost of improved cattle breeds is very high so the poor and marginal dairy farmers could not afford it. Majority (82.66 per cent) of the dairy farmers faced a problem *viz.* increase in expenditure on cattle management, fodder and labour in dairy enterprise. These findings are in line with the findings of Taral *et al.* (2020), Kadam *et al.* (2019), Buragohain (2020), who opined that feeding of balanced rations to the dairy animals was the main constraints for unavailability of the concentrate feed ingredients and higher cost involved for purchasing them from outside the state in Aizawl District of Mizoram. Similarly, Sujatha *et al.* (2015) also reported that majority of the farmers (81.67%) opined that, high-cost feed is the major constraint in milk production and marketing followed by low productivity of milch animals (60.00%) in some districts of Andhra Pradesh.

The 47.33 per cent member respondents reported that impracticability in using highly technosive machineries due to small herd size was the constraint in dairy enterprise. More than three-fourth (76.66 per cent) of member respondents had faced the problem that lack of land availability for fodder cultivation and pasture management. Difficulty in controlling contagious and parasitic diseases of animals was the problem faced by 70.66 per cent of member respondents. The 68.00 per cent of member respondents reported that they faced the problem that lack of training programmes needed to raise the knowledge regarding dairy enterprise. These findings were also in line with Lalruatfeli *et al.* (2021), Singodia *et al.* (2019), Shinde *et al.* (2018) and Atkare *et al.* (2017) that more distance of VH/ care-center, inaccessibility of veterinarians or para-veterinary staff, inadequate training and extension services and lack of proper advisory services on scientific feeding, breeding management were perceived as 'serious constraints' by livestock farmers.

37.33 per cent of member respondents had expressed the problem of lack of co-ordination between office bearers, planning and executive staff with co-operative dairy members, followed by 40.66 per cent of member respondents were having the problem *i.e.*, negligence towards the opinion of member beneficiaries while implementing new scheme. Lack of proper information on the recent dairy management technologies was the problem mentioned by nearly three-fifth (58.66 per cent) of member respondents.

Suggestions made by the members of dairy co-operative societies to overcome the problems

Suggestions were obtained from respondents to overcome the problems faced by them in dairy enterprise. Following are the major suggestions made by the member respondents shown in the Table 2.

Data revealed that, majority of member respondent dairy farmers made suggestions like; providing knowledge regarding handling of machine milking (84.00 per cent) followed by enhance milk price for the producers (81.33 per cent). The 75.33 per cent member respondents suggested that the loan amount for the purchase dairy animals should be increased whereas more than three-fifth (64.66 per cent) member respondents suggested that loan sanction procedure should be easy. The 68.66 per cent of member respondents made suggestion that there should be training programmes regarding recent dairy technology practices at regular interval followed by subsidies should be given on certain inputs like veterinary medicines, fodder, seeds, concentrate, ration, etc. (61.33 per cent). The suggestion like regular and planned supply of vaccine made by 48.00 per cent of member respondents, better co-ordination between office bearers, planning and executive staff with co-operative dairy members made by 34.66 per cent of member respondents of co-operative dairy society. The suggestions of Mohad *et al.* (2020) are conformity with present suggestions which conclude that there is need to organize awareness programme, demonstrate scientific feeding and management practices to increase the production performance of kadhani cattle and efficiency of male for draft purpose.

Table 1. Problems faced by the co-operative dairy members in dairy business activities

Sr. No.	Problems	Respondent (N= 150)		Rank
		No.	%	
1	High cost of improved cattle breeds	136	90.66	I
2	Increase in expenditure on cattle management, fodder and labour	124	82.66	II
3	Lack of land availability for fodder cultivation and pasture management	115	76.66	III
4	Difficulty in controlling contagious and parasitic diseases of animals	106	70.66	IV
5	Lack of training programmes needed to raise the knowledge regarding dairy enterprise	102	68.00	V
6	Lack of proper information on the recent dairy management technologies	88	58.66	VI
7	Due to small herd size use of highly technosive machineries are impracticable	71	47.33	VII
8	Negligence towards the opinion of member while implementing new scheme	61	40.66	VIII
9	Lack of co-ordination between office bearers, planning and executive staff with co-operative dairy members	56	37.33	IX

Table 2. Suggestions made by member respondents to overcome the problems

Sr. No.	Suggestions	Respondent (N=150)		Rank
		No.	%	
1	Providing knowledge regarding handling of milking machine	126	84.00	I
2	Enhance milk price for the producers	122	81.33	II
3	The loan amount for the purchase dairy animals be increased	113	75.33	III
4	Provide training programmes regarding recent dairy technology practices at regular interval	103	68.66	IV
5	Loan sanction procedure should be easy	97	64.66	V
6	Subsidies should be given on certain inputs like veterinary medicines, fodder, seeds, concentrate, ration, etc.	92	61.33	VI
7	There should be regular and planned supply of vaccine	72	48.00	VII
8	There should be better co-ordination between office bearers, planning and executive staff with co-operative dairy members	52	34.66	VIII

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